

ACADEMIC RESILIENCE AND SELF-EFFICACY OF GRADE 7 STUDENTS IN ARALING PANLIPUNAN AT CALAMBA CITY SCIENCE INTEGRATED SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

Academic resilience is the ability of students to achieve good educational outcomes despite adversity (Young Minds UK, 2020). Self-efficacy, on the other hand, pertains to a person's belief in his/her capacity to succeed in a particular situation (Bandura, 1977). With the ongoing pandemic, students are greatly affected now that they are undergoing a new normal war of education. Thus, this study aimed to determine the relationship between academic resilience and self-efficacy of Grade 7 students in Araling Panlipunan at Calamba City Science Integrated School. Specifically, academic resilience is divided into perseverance, reflecting and adaptive help-seeking, and negative affect and emotion response. On the other hand, self-efficacy is divided into perceived control, competence, persistence, and self-regulated learning. Descriptive-correlative design was used with the aid of mean, standard deviation, two-tailed t-test, Pearson product moment correlation coefficient, and multiple linear regression analysis. Results showed that students are 'Likely' to manifest academic resilience and students "Agree" that they possess self-efficacy. No significant difference is revealed when academic resilience and self-efficacy is categorized as to gender and learning modality. Correlational analysis showed a significant relationship between academic resilience and self-efficacy of students. Multiple regression analyses revealed that all parameters of academic resilience significantly predict the self-efficacy of students in terms of perceived control and self-regulated learning. Competence can be predicted by reflecting and adaptive help-seeking and negative affect and emotion responses, while persistence can be predicted by perseverance alone.

Keywords: Education, Social Science, Academic Resilience, Self-Efficacy, Descriptive Design, Correlative Design, Inferential Statistics, Philippines